

SOME COMMENTS ON THE USE OF LATIN CHEMICAL TERMS IN MEDICINE

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Abstract. This article discusses the naming, dictionary form, and usage of chemical terms used in medicine in Latin and English. In addition to naming chemical terms in medicine in terms of form, they are also used in other sciences with the same name, their properties are complete. information is provided.

Key words: chemical terminology, information, elements, recommendation, oxide, anion, carbon, complex.

Introduction

Usage are number as a left superscript, as ^{14}C , is gradually governed by the International Union of Pure and becoming universal. Ratios, however, are generally Applied Chemistry (IUPAC). Various commissions more readable if the superscript follows the symbol, within the IUPAC periodically update, revise, or as $\text{Rb}^{85}/\text{Rb}^{87}$. Thus, an admixture of the two practices, clarify terminology in many areas of specialty.

Consequently, the purpose of the study is to conduct a structural-semantic, orthographic and prosodic analysis of some chemical terms in medicine to identify differences in their structure, meanings, accents, and spelling in English and taking into account these differences when transmitting the lexical units All these differences represent importance when translating terms from one language to another. Accounting, for example, structure of a multicomponent term, allows you to identify the main and dependent words, their relationships and interdependencies, which determines adequacy of their transmission. Differences in the typological structure of these languages necessitates studying the composition of terms in them

These even in the same paper, seems permissible. If the revisions appear as recommendation articles in "Pure author chooses to use the form $\text{Rb}^{85}/\text{Rb}^{87}$, it should be and Applied Chemistry," the official journal of the used consistently for all ratios.

Modern medical terminology is the result centuries-old development of world healing and medical science. Medical terminology is presented in different national languages and includes a significant proportion of common linguistic origins lexical and word-formation units, as well as general structural models. This etymological, word-formation and structural community of the terms under consideration is determined by the all-encompassing stable influence for many centuries and, especially now, two classical languages of the ancient world - ancient Greek and Latin. Despite the etymological, word-formation and structural common roots of medical terms, the study showed the presence significant differences in these terms, ignoring which can lead to a highly distorted perception in oral and written speech of medical representatives in different countries. In the scientific community, the interpretation of the concept of "term" exists many approaches based mainly on two concepts. Proponents of the first concept advocate "unambiguity, brevity, the ability of a term to express a strictly fixed concept", calling terms in special words.

In other words, the properties of the term minimized in their content characteristics and brought to the negative antipodes of the corresponding properties of commonly used words. Another concept proposed by G.O. Vinokur, considering terms not as special words, but as words in a special function Where the full name IUPAC. Recommendations published through 1979 of an element is used in text matter, the mass Numara available in a handbook (International Union of bar is presented with a hyphen, as carbon-14.

The Pure and Applied Chemistry, 1979), which is com- atomic number is commonly omitted but, if used, is manly referred to the "green book" of the IUPAC. Written as a left subscript: $1:\sim$. Ionic charge is always Recent editions of the Chemical here Company's indicated as a superscript numeral followed by a plus (CRC) "Handbook of Chemistry and Physics" (West, or minus sign. 1984) also contain much of this information. IUPAC rules call for use of Greek terms for Chemical names, rather than symbols, are generally adjectives and prefixes pertaining to valences and used in text except for the following: other stoichiometric properties.

Percent of the oxides present. This practice naturally 2. In a complex term: Ca-Mg-SO₃-NO, solution. Leads geologists to describe chemical changes in terms 3, In proximity: Ca⁺ and Mg⁺ ions combine with of the oxides, as "The introduction of silica and aluCO₃- and SO₄⁻, respectively. This usage is generally proper, but

inconsistencies may arise because Symbols should also be used in tables and equations there is no convenient term for total iron oxides. Conan within text where failure to do so would result sider, for example the sentence "Silica, magnesia, and in complex or ambiguous terms. A table of atomic iron were introduced," in which two oxides and one names, symbols, and weights (International Union of element are mentioned. Such difficulties can be Pure and Applied Chemistry, 1984) is reproduced in avoided by describing chemical changes in terms of table 2, in the section on "Abbreviations, Signs, and elements or perhaps by using the Symbols." for the several oxides.

The names of more complex compositions are translated similarly. compounds [3, p. 40]. An example is complex salts and acids: $K[AuCl_4]$ – (“potassium tetrachloroaurate (III)” – “potassium tetrachloroaurate (III)”), $H[PF_6]$ (“hydrogen hexafluorophosphate”). However, there are a number of compounds historically accepted traditional whose names do not follow the rules, but have not yet been released out of use and are even preferred [3, p.27], for example: H_2O (“water” – “water” or “hydrogen oxide”), NH_3 (“ammonia” – “ammonia” or “nitrogen hydride”). For a number of compounds, the names are outdated are used by scientists in the scientific community along with variant names, accepted according to the rules: $Na_2B_4O_7 \cdot 10H_2O$ (“sodium tetraborate” or “boron” – “sodium tetraborate” or “borax”), SiO_2 (“silicon dioxide” or “silica” – “silicon dioxide” or “silica”). When considering the features of writing terms in English existing in scientific exception environment. For example, “hydrogen bromide” is translated as “hydrogen bromide”, but due to the fact that for hydrogen compounds of halogens it is allowed to use names of a different type, also correct will be considered “bromine hydride” (“chlorin hydride” – “hydrogen chloride”).

This research work develops the fundamentals of studying chemical terminological vocabulary in medicine in two different languages. The study carried out an analysis of structural-semantic, some spelling and prosodic features of certain chemical and medical terms. Further prospects for research work in this direction are seen in a more detailed consideration of individual thematic groups medical terminology. In modern times, it seems relevant to study various aspects of medical terminology based on means computer information technologies.

Correct usage of chemical symbols as dictated by Any table reporting chemical analyses should clearly the International Union of Pure and Applied distinguish

between reporting oxides and ions. Most Chemistry is illustrated as follows: researchers follow the reporting scheme used in Deer and others (1966) in which analyses are reported from highest to lowest oxidation-state cations (as oxides) followed by anions. The rare earth elements should Field Contents never be referred to as rare earths.

Literature:

1. Abduvasievna, G. S., Habibdjanovna, B. D., Karimovna, Y. S., Ugli, K. Y. S., Ugli, B. S. A., & Shukhratovna, N. F. (2021). Foreign Language Teachers in the System of Public Education. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 7001-7010.
2. Karimovna, Y. S. (2022). STRATEGIC METHODS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK MEDICAL DISCOURSES. *Thematics Journal of Education*, 7(5).
3. Karimovna, Y. S. (2023). SPECIAL TYPE OF MEDICAL SPEECH IN THE COMMUNICATION PROCESS. *Research Focus International Scientific Journal*, 2(4), 115-120.
4. Karimovna, Y. S., & Rashid, A. (2023, November). ANATOMICAL TERMINOLOGY. In *Konferensiyalar| Conferences* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 101-104).
5. Karimovna, Y. S., & Zara, A. (2023). EXPLORING THE LATIN ROOTS OF CHEMICAL TERMINOLOGY: NAMES OF CHEMICAL ELEMENTS, ACIDS, AND OXIDES. *Yangi O'zbekistonda Tabiiy va Ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar respublika ilmiy amaliy konferensiyasi*, 1(7), 8-13.
6. Yorova, S., & Nasimova, S. ELECTRONIC COLLECTED MATERIALS OF XI JUNIOR RESEARCHERS'CONFERENCE 2019 Linguistics, literature, philology 7 UDC 372.881 THE WAYS OF TEACHING LANGUAGES AT MEDICAL INSTITUTIONS Samarkand State Medical Institute.
7. Karimovna, Y. S., & Zulkarnain, S. (2023, November). DEGREES OF COMPARISON OF ADJECTIVES AND COORDINATION WITH NOUNS OF FIFTH DECLENSION. In *Konferensiyalar| Conferences* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 80-82).
8. Karimovna, Y. S. (2022). The linguistic environment in the field of medical communications. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 2(2), 143-147.
9. Karimovna, Y. S. Social-cultural Characteristics of Uzbek and English Medical Speech. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 4(5), 294-298.

10. Karimovna, Y. S. Medicine and Education faculty Samarkand State Medical Institute.
11. Shodikulova, A. Z. (2021, December). The theory of an integrative approach to the analysis of the phenomenon of metonymy. In *Archive of Conferences* (pp. 56-57).
12. Shodikulova, A. (2023). COHESIONS FORMED BY MEANS OF HYPONYMS. *Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры*, 3(9), 40-43.
13. Shodikulova, A. Z. (2021). The text is about the phenomenon of cohesion. *Academicia Globe*, 2(05), 229-232.
14. Shodikulova, A. Z. (2022). The analysis of the phenomenon of metonymy. *Science and Education*, 3(12), 1136-1140.
15. Shodikulova, A. Z. (2021). Methodology For Using Computer Training Programs In English Lessons. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education (TURCOMAT)*, 12(13), 3358-3367.
16. SHODIKULOVA, A. Z. (2021). THE ROLE OF METONYMS IN THE FORMATION OF TEXT STRUCTURE. *THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCE Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука*, (9), 655-658.
17. Zikiriyayevna, S. A. (2023). JAHON ADABIYOTI NAMOYONDASI JEYMS JOYS HIKOYALARI. " XXI ASRDA INNOVATION TEXNOLOGIYALAR, FAN VA TA'LIM TARAQQIYOTIDAGI DOLZARB MUAMMOLAR" nomli respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi, 1(10), 123-125.
18. Anatolevna, F. M., & Zikiriyayevna, S. A. (2023). DEONTOLOGICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF WINGED SAYINGS IN MEDICINE. *Ethiopian International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 10(10), 124-125.
19. Zikiriyayevna, S. A. COGNITIVE-DISCURSIVE ASPECTS OF IMPLEMENTATION OF METONYMY IN A MEDIA.
20. Zikiriyayevna, S. A. (2022). DISCURSIVE ANALYSIS OF DERIVED METONYMY. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 1588-1592.
21. Shodikulova, A. Z. (2021). COGNITIVE INTERPRETATION OF THE PHENOMENON OF METONYMY. *Scientific reports of Bukhara State University*, 5(1), 136-146.

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22. Ilhomovna, I. S., & Zikiriyayevna, S. A. (2023). LEARNING ENGLISH LANGUAGE AS A SECOND LANGUAGE. *Yangi O'zbekistonda Tabiiy va Ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar respublika ilmiy amaliy konferensiyasi*, 1(7), 37-43.
23. Zikiriyayevna, S. A. (2022). Cognitive Interpretation Of The Phenomenon Of Metonymy. *Eurasian Medical Research Periodical*, 5, 102-104.
24. Zikiriyayevna, S. A. (2023). THE ENCOUNTER OF MODERNISM IN ENGLISH LITERATURE. *Ethiopian International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 10(12), 6-8.
25. МЕТОНЫМУ, О. a teacher of department of languages, Medicine and Education faculty Samarkand State Medical Institute. *SCIENTIFIC REPORTS OF BUKHARA STATE UNIVERSITY*, 136(17), 49-52.
26. Шодикулова, А. З. (2023). ГИПОНИМЛАР ҚЎЛЛАНИШИДА КОГЕЗИЯНИНГ НАМОЁН БЎЛИШИ. " XXI ASRDA INNOVATION TEXNOLOGIYALAR, FAN VA TA'LIM TARAQQIYOTIDAGI DOLZARB MUAMMOLAR" nomli respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi, 1(11), 111-117.
27. Махмудова, С. А. (2022). Репрезентация концептуальной оппозиции " свой/чужой" в романе Дж. Олдриджа " Горы и Оружие". *Вестник Челябинского государственного университета*, (9 (467)), 153-160.
28. Махмудова, С. А. (2022). ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНОЙ ОППОЗИЦИИ «СВОЙ/ЧУЖОЙ» В ТРИАДУ «ДРУГОЙ-СВОЙ–ДРУГ» В РОМАНЕ ДЖ. ОЛДРИДЖА «I DON'T WANT HIM TO DIE» («НЕ ХОЧУ, ЧТОБЫ ОН УМИРАЛ»). *МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА*, 5(5).
29. Махмудова, С. А. (2023). РЕПРЕЗЕНТАЦИЯ ПЕРСОНАЖНОГО КОНЦЕПТА «АНГЛИЧАНИН» В РОМАНЕ ДЖ. ОЛДРИДЖА «ДИПЛОМАТ». *Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences*, 420-427.
30. Махмудова, С. А. (2023). ОСОБЕННОСТИ РЕПРЕЗЕНТАЦИИ БИНАРНОЙ ОППОЗИЦИИ «СВОЙ/ЧУЖОЙ» В РАЗНЫХ ПРОСТРАНСТВАХ РОМАНА ДЖ. ОЛДРИДЖА «ДИПЛОМАТ». *European Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development*, 17, 125-132.

31. Махмудова, С. А. (2023, June). ТРИАДА «ДРУГОЙ-СВОЙ-ДРУГ» В «ВОСТОЧНЫХ» РОМАНАХ ДЖ. ОЛДРИДЖА. In *E Conference Zone* (pp. 69-73).
32. Махмудова, С. А. (2023, June). РОЛЬ БИНАРНОЙ ОППОЗИЦИИ «СВОЙ-ЧУЖОЙ» В РОМАНЕ ДЖ. ОЛДРИДЖА «ГОРЫ И ОРУЖИЕ». In *E Conference Zone* (pp. 74-77).
33. Bakhodirovna, E. M., & Amina, S. (2023, November). DEGREES OF ADJECTIVES. GRAMMAR CATEGORIES. In *International conference on multidisciplinary science* (Vol. 1, No. 5, pp. 230-233).
34. Genzhebaevna, A. P., & Baxadirovna, E. M. (2023). THE ROLE OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN MEDICAL UNIVERSITY. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 12(11), 49-52.
35. Bakhodirovna, E. M., & Saqib, T. (2023). PHARMACEUTICAL TERMINOLOGY. *Yangi O'zbekistonda Tabiiy va Ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar respublika ilmiy amaliy konferensiyasi*, 1(7), 76-80.
36. Bakhodirovna, E. M., & Saqib, T. (2023). PHARMACEUTICAL TERMINOLOGY. *Yangi O'zbekistonda Tabiiy va Ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar respublika ilmiy amaliy konferensiyasi*, 1(7), 76-80.
37. Karimovna, Y. S., Kenjabaevna, A. P., Bakhodirovna, E. M., & Mallaevna, N. S. (2023). PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN THE MEDICAL FIELD OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK CULTURES. DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATIONS IN SCIENCE, 2 (2), 10–13.
38. Эсанова, М. Б. (2022). Инглиз ва ўзбек тилларидаги қўшма гапларнинг тўсиқсиз маъноли турлари. *Science and Education*, 3(11), 1372-1375.
39. Sharipov, B. (2023). SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON THE FORMATION OF CLINICAL TERMS IN LATIN. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(6), 477-479.
40. Salimovich, S. B. (2022). RECIPROCAL SYMMETRY AND ITS GRAMMATICAL INDICATIONS. *EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD)*, 7(12), 129-131.
41. Sharipov, B. (2022). RETSIPROKLIK XUSUSIDA MULOHAZALAR. *Общественные науки в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования*, 1(19), 63-66.
42. Salimovich, S. B. (2022, January). FUNCTIONS OF LANGUAGE UNITS. In *Conference Zone* (pp. 62-63).

